

The effect of hydrogen addition on the amplitude and harmonic response of azimuthal instabilities in a pressurized annular combustor

Supplemental material S1: Acoustic characterization

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The acoustic characterization of several elements is done following the approach detailed in [1, 2]. The measurement setup is shown in Fig. 1. Two identical pipes with an inner diameter of 19 mm and 4 microphone ports were used. In the figure, both horn drivers are mounted however a total of five independent states was measured for each probe: left open - speaker right, left closed - speaker right, speaker left - speaker right, speaker left - right closed and speaker left - right open. The investigated frequency range was 100-3000 Hz. The method was validated by the investigation of an open pipe which resulted in the expected behavior without reflection (see Fig. 2). The result for the different elements of the combustor are shown in Figs. 3-5. Subsequently the sintered metal plate is highly reflective, practically isolating the combustion chamber from the plenum. The acoustic behavior of the swirler and the glass bead section is highly dependent on the frequency.

References

- [1] M. Åbom, Measurement of the scattering-matrix of acoustical two-ports, *Mech. Syst. Signal Pr.* 5 (1991) 89–104.
[2] P. Davies, Practical flow duct acoustics, *J. Sound Vib.* 124 (1) (1988) 91–115.

Figure 1: Impedance measurement setup

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Figure 2: Scattering matrix for the open pipe

Figure 3: Scattering matrix for the sintered metal plate

Figure 4: Scattering matrix for the swirler

Figure 5: Scattering matrix the the glass bead section